

FINANCIAL AWARENESS AND ITS ROLE IN INVESTMENT BEHAVIOUR: A STUDY FOCUSED ON NON-WORKING WOMEN FROM KARNATAKA

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ABSTRACT

Women are increasingly assuming significant financial responsibilities in an era characterized by rapid transformations within the financial domain. These developments necessitate an in-depth understanding of the evolving gender disparities embedded within contemporary socio-economic systems, as well as a systematic evaluation of pivotal areas required to mitigate these inequities. This study seeks to validate or challenge the notion that barriers exist which prevent women's financial knowledge from being effectively translated into actionable behaviour's, through a comprehensive literature review and an online survey. The findings indicate that while the majority of working women demonstrate awareness of investment avenues and exhibit prudent financial practices, non-working women often remain uninformed. Moreover, the study underscores that non-working women who engage in saving, borrowing, investing, and systematically planning their financial needs are more inclined towards achieving financial independence.

Keywords: Financial Literacy, Financial Planning, Investment Behaviour, Non-Working Women, Financial Needs.

1. INTRODUCTION

Learning how to manage one's finances is something that should be prioritised from the very beginning of one's professional life onward. It facilitates financial planning, instils saving habits, and increases financial product awareness, resulting in more effective use of financial services by the general public. The majority of countries around the world confront a huge difficulty in financial literacy. In the backdrop of the global financial crisis and financial inclusion, the concept of financial literacy has piqued the interest of researchers, policymakers, academicians, international bodies, governments and their agencies, and other stakeholders. People with financial literacy are better able to make changes for the betterment of their social, cultural, economic, and environmental circumstances. It has frequently resulted in decision-making in areas such as product investment, household savings, budgeting, stocks market, housing loan, real estate, insurance, credit card, tax planning, pension and retirement security, and so on.¹

¹ Atkinson, A. and F. Messy (2012), "Measuring Financial Literacy: Results of the OECD International Network on Financial Education (INFE) Pilot Study", OECD Working Papers on Finance, Insurance and Private Pensions, No. 15, OECD Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/5k9csfs90fr4-en>

Financial education is widely recognised as a critical component for individual financial well-being as well as a country's financial stability. Consumers are now entering a risky market where they are presented with a diverse range of financial products and services. Financial literacy is the capacity to manage money in simple terms. It refers to a person's knowledge and grasp of financial ideas, as well as their ability to use them confidently and responsibly to make sound financial decisions. In recent years, financial literacy has become a major area all around the world. Because of the increasing complexity of the financial market, financial innovations and the resulting development of new products, easier access to credit and financial instruments, and the shift from defined pension schemes to "do it yourself" schemes, the concept of financial literacy is gaining traction. The global financial crisis has also brought to light the terrible effects of making financial decisions without sufficient information.

1.1 DEFINITION AND CONCEPT- FINANCIAL LITERACY

Simply said, financial literacy is the capacity to manage money. It broadly refers to the knowledge and understanding of financial ideas; the capacity to apply it confidently and responsibly to make educated decisions for the individual's financial well-being. Financial Education is defined by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) as "the process by which financial consumers/investors improve their understanding of financial products, concepts, and risks, and acquire the skills and self assurance to become aware of (financial) opportunities and threats, to make informed choices, to know where to go for help, and to take other effective actions to immunise themselves." ²

Financial education is broadly defined as "the ability to be familiar with and understand financial market products, particularly rewards and dangers, in order to make informed decisions." From this perspective, financial education largely refers to personal financial education that enables individuals to take effective steps to increase overall well-being and prevent financial distress." ³

1.2 IMPORTANCE OF FINANCIAL LITERACY

Financial literacy is widely regarded as a crucial life skill for consumers in today's ever-increasingly complex markets. The continuously evolving and financially sophisticated economy offers users with new challenges. They must improve their financial skills in order to capitalise on financial innovations. Recognizing the importance of financial literacy for a country's economic growth and financial stability, governments around the world are working harder to increase people's financial literacy.

- Consumers nowadays have access to a wide range of financial products and services provided by large service providers. While meeting comparable demands, they are creating a frenzy of misunderstanding among customers and investors. The market's complexity makes it difficult for the average person to make informed financial and investment decisions and survive in the market. When customers are naïve and unfamiliar with financial problems, these possibilities tend to accelerate the riskiness of decisions. Consumers must be educated about their options, grasp the cost-benefit

² OECD (2005). Recommendation on Principles and Good Practices for Financial Education and Awareness OECD Publishing. Retrieved from <http://www.oecd.org/finance/financial-education/35108560.pdf>

³ Chakrabarty, K. C. (2009). Furthering financial inclusion through financial literacy and credit counseling. RBI Monthly Bulletin, (December), 2361-2366. Retrieved from <http://rbidocs.rbi.org.in/rdocs/Bulletin/PDFs/5FFIBUL1209.pdf>

relationship, and act proactively in order to make sound financial decisions. Financial education sessions are essential for investors to teach sensible investment behaviour.

- Technological advancements have transformed the financial market. Exposure to new communication technology, such as email marketing and social marketing, has presented customers with a wealth of product information. Many times, these elegantly wrapped adverts are deceptive, and people are duped. Financial knowledge and awareness are becoming increasingly vital for maximising the benefits of technological innovation and upgrading and coping with these obstacles.
- In today's financial landscape, defined benefit pension plans are quickly being supplanted by defined contribution pension plans. Employees are increasingly responsible for managing their retirement plans. They must make judgments on pension plans, contributions to schemes, investment portfolios, and withdrawals. These selections carry the risk of poor savings, cautious investment contributions, insufficient retirement money, and losing assets due to market changes. The severity increases in the case of inflation, employee longevity, and financial market catastrophe.⁴ Employee financial education is the only solution to all of these financial concerns and difficulties.

1.3 FINANCIAL PLANNING

Today's fast-changing economic situations are frequently uncertain. This makes it difficult for the general population to prepare their financial situation, whether in the short or long term. With so much unpredictability, it's critical to have a solid financial plan in place for future economic conditions. This prudent financial planning can help to preserve and avert undesirable conditions in the community. Financial management is a subset of financial planning. Financial management is a science that teaches you how to plan, analyse, and regulate your finances. Financial planning is the process of estimating a company's future position and financial status (it can be short-term or long-term). The financial plan is built on a set of assumptions (scenarios), both of which are concerned with the link between financial variables and financial actions.

The Financial Planning Standards Board Indonesia defines financial planning as the process of accomplishing one's life goals through integrated and planned financial management.⁵ Financial planning, according to Prita Hapsari Ghozic, is a process in which an individual attempts to achieve his financial goals by developing and implementing a complete financial plan. Good financial planning will result in a clear financial plan that will help the plan owner reach his financial objectives. This financial plan is akin to a blueprint that shows where an individual's or family's financial situation will go in the future.⁶

1.4 FINANCIAL PLANNING AND INVESTMENT BEHAVIOUR

It's not just about investing when it comes to financial planning. A business plan can be used in a variety of ways during the life of an economic cycle. Everyone earns money to attain one or more of their life goals around the world. People use the money for pure goals, such as

⁴ Munnell, A. H., Aubry, J. P., Hurwitz, J., & Quinby, L. (2011). A role for defined contribution plans in the public sector. Retrieved from http://crr.bc.edu/wp-content/uploads/2011/04/slp_16-508.pdf

⁵ Palameta, B., Nguyen, C., Hui, T.S.W., & Gyarmati, D. (2016). The link between financial confidence and financial outcomes among working-aged Canadians. The Social Research and Demonstration Corporation (SRDC).

⁶ Prita Hapsari Ghozic. (2019). *Make It Happen! Smart Book of Financial Plans to Realize Dreams* (7th Printing) Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka Utama

funding daily needs or purchasing exotic pleasures in order to live a better life. Individual financial planning and investing are an important aspect of anyone's life, especially in today's world, where everything is measured in terms of money. In comparison to the life duration, the active working span of a human life is brief. It suggests that people will spend roughly the same number of years after retirement as they did during their working lives. As a result, it becomes critical to save and invest while working in order for people to continue to earn money and live comfortably. Financial planning allows a person to determine their goals and objectives, assess their existing situation, and take necessary steps to attain their objectives. A person can live a comfortable and secure economic life with adequate financial planning.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Krishna Achyut (2021)⁷ mentioned about financial literacy and women's attitudes on financial planning and investment. The research is being carried out in the Dhubri district, using a well-designed and well-structured questionnaire with 200 respondents. The data was gathered from both primary and secondary sources, and it was analysed using simple percentages, mean scores, and standard deviation, as well as a t-test to evaluate the hypothesis. The study's findings provide insight into the participants' financial literacy as well as their attitudes about financial planning and investment.

Wani Fitriah (2021)⁸ described about how financial literacy and financial inclusion affected Palembang's financial planning. In this study, the population was limitless, and the sample size was 200 people. The information used in this study was derived from original sources. The data was gathered through the use of a questionnaire. At the analysis stage, qualitative data is combined with quantitative data. The findings revealed that the F test (combined) for financial literacy and financial inclusion factors had a favourable and significant impact on Palembang residents' financial planning. The financial literacy variable had a positive and substantial influence on the financial planning of the inhabitants of Palembang, according to the results of the t test (individually).

Laith Yousef Banihani (2020)⁹ explained that financial planning is the process of reviewing an individual's financial goals, taking money owed to him, setting life goals, and then taking the required actions to attain those goals within the time frame set. It is a method of calculating a person's financial requirements. The study's goal is to define the investor's financial resource strategy and to provide an overview of the investor's immediate and long-term objectives. The researcher gathered primary data by interviewing investors about their investment goals and risk tolerance. Financial planning is a dynamic and adaptable concept that comprises regular and methodical examination, proper management, judgement, and actions, according to the findings.

3. RESEARCH GAP

In Western countries, and increasingly in Asia, the majority of studies have looked into the link between financial literacy and wealth increase. In the Indian setting, there has not been

⁷Krishna Achyut, Borah, Samsuddoha Ahmed (2021) Financial Literacy and Attitude of Women towards Financial Planning and Investment: A Case Study in Dhubri District of Assam, *International Journal for Modern Trends in Science and Technology* 7(10):194-201

⁸Wani Fitriah (2021) Financial Literacy and Financial Inclusion on the Financial Planning of the city of Palembang, *Review of Management and Entrepreneurship* 5(1):19-32

⁹Laith Yousef Banihani (2020) A Study of Financial Planning and Investment of Individual, *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)* 9(11):5

much research done. In terms of the influence of demographic characteristics (age, gender, education level, employment, and income level) on women's investment behaviour, very little research has been done. This study looks into the impact of demographics (gender, age, education level, etc.) on financial literacy and financial planning, as well as their impact on investment behaviour among non-working women in Karnataka. According to the existing researches, a number of studies on financial literacy across diverse demographics in India have been undertaken, but no thorough study on financial literacy among non-working women has been conducted. Because women account for half of India's demographic dividends, it is critical to reduce financial education hurdles for women so that they can become financially self-sufficient. Thus, the current study aims to fill that gap in this study by investigating the impact of financial literacy and financial planning among non-salaried women.

4. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The ability to read and understand financial statements should be a driving concern worldwide. Financial literacy is the result of a high number of financial resources, many financial schemes, and a poor level of financial knowledge. Women's lack of understanding and trust in money management and investing programmes has a negative impact on their capacity to achieve their financial goals. People's financial awareness varies depending on their literacy and perceptual levels. Working women have more opportunities and are more self-sufficient than non-working women in terms of financial problems. Consequently, working women are better at making financial decisions than non-working women. Non-working women's financial decisions are influenced by their family and household income. In making financial decisions, family, emotion, and society all play a part. Financial decision-making confidence suffers as a result of a lack of information of financial products. This research addresses these issues by finding the elements that allow non-working women to be financially independent.

5. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Due to a lack of confidence, financial knowledge, abilities, and understanding of financial concepts, non-salaried women are afraid to make financial decisions. Financial literacy is required for women to develop financial skills and confidence so that they can actively participate in home financial planning. Various studies have demonstrated that financially knowledgeable women helped to minimise household poverty and enhance their family's living situations to a considerable extent. Women's financial knowledge must be raised in order for them to make better financial decisions and to improve their social and financial position. It is also vital to increase women's financial literacy in order to assure their active engagement in not just their households, but also in the economy. Women's financial independence can be achieved through financial knowledge. Financial independence boosts a person's self-esteem and allows them to take part in family financial planning. This study will look at various institutions' efforts to promote financial literacy, financial planning and investment among non-working women in Karnataka.

6. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To explore the significance of financial literacy and financial planning among non-working women in Karnataka
- To study the impact of financial literacy and financial planning on investment behaviour among non-working women in Karnataka

- To provide suggestions based on the study to enhance the investment behaviour of non-working women in Karnataka

7. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

By providing suitable recommendations, the current study will help to improve financial literacy and financial planning of non-working women. The study will fill a knowledge gap because this topic has not been widely researched in Karnataka. This research will examine the impact of financial literacy on individual investment decisions among non-working women, thereby raising their understanding about why saving and investing is worthwhile and how financial planning makes them self-dependent.

8. PROFILE OF KARNATAKA

Karnataka, India's seventh largest state is located in the country's South-West side. When the state was known as the State of Mysore, it had a long and illustrious history. It was just a few decades ago, in 1973, that it was called Karnataka. The state has a rich history, vibrant culture, stunning geographical characteristics, a thriving economy, and well-educated citizens. It is divided into 30 districts, each of which contains a number of educational institutions, large corporations, banks, hotels, hospitals, religious sites, and recreational areas.

- **Economy of Karnataka**

Different sectors benefit each state and contribute to its economic growth and development. Karnataka is one of the states in India with the fastest economic growth. The following are the many industries that contribute to the Karnataka economy: Agriculture, Forestry, Logging, Fishing, and Animal Husbandry are the state's principal economic sectors. Manufacturing, electricity, gas, mining, quarrying, and water delivery make up Karnataka's secondary economy. Banking, business services, insurance, education, public administration, transportation, hotel, real estate, restaurant, trade, communication, storage and various other services make up the state's tertiary economy.¹⁰

- **Centre For Financial Literacy (CFL)**

The CFL pilot project on financial literacy was launched by RBI in 2017 in nine states and eighty blocks by six non-governmental organisations (NGOs) in partnership with eight sponsor banks for a three-year period, with funding from NABARD's Financial Inclusion Fund (FIF) and respective banks. RBI chose the NGOs that were registered with the DEA Fund Cell, DoR for the project after a thorough screening process. The goal of the study was to look at novel and interactive ways to financial literacy. The expansion of CFLs to every block in the country is one of the goals of the National Strategy for Financial Inclusion (NSFI: 2019-2024). As part of the FL process, RBI has chosen three adjacent blocks that will be served with CFLs. The Reserve Bank of India has designated 114 blocks in Karnataka for this purpose. DHAN Foundation and MOTHER Ron, two NGOs in the state, have been identified as CFLs.¹¹

¹⁰<https://www.karnatakaonline.in/about/profile>

¹¹<http://slbckarnataka.com/CFL.aspx>

9. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The current research employed a descriptive and empirical research design. For the purpose of data collection, the researcher used both primary and secondary sources. In terms of primary data, a well-structured questionnaire was used to collect information. The majority of the data came from original sources, with a little amount coming from secondary sources such as journals, books, and websites. The current investigation is being carried out by the researcher employing a basic convenience sample technique. The districts of Bangalore, Bellary, Belgaum, and Mysore were chosen from the state of Karnataka for the study, with a total sample size of 209 respondents. Different statistical tools were used to analyse the data. The current study's research design is described in Table No. 1:

TABLE NO: 1
RESEARCH DESIGN

Research Design	Research Methodology	Description
Research Type	Descriptive research	It entails gathering and categorising qualitative information categories, as well as organising, tabulating, and describing the data.
	Empirical research	Analysis and interpretation of collected data
Data Collection	Primary source	The data was collected primarily through a survey with the help of structured questionnaires related to financial literacy and its impact on financial planning and investment behaviour based on a 5-point Likert Scale from Strongly Disagree (S.D) to Strongly Agree (S.A) prepared for non-working women residing in selected districts of Karnataka (Bangalore, Bellary, Belgaum, and Mysore).
	Secondary source	Books, journals and periodicals, newspapers and magazines, internet, and other sources of information are used.
Sampling	Sampling technique	The current study used the convenience sampling method. This procedure is used since it is the least expensive and takes the least amount of time.
	Sample size population	Non-working women from four Karnataka districts (Bangalore, Bellary, Belgaum, and Mysore).
	Sample size	209
Testing of Hypotheses	Statistical tools	Anova, correlation, Chi-square, SEM, and other statistical methods were employed.
Analysis of Data	Software used	The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and AMOS version 20 were used to analyse the collected primary data and test hypotheses.

Source: Self-prepared by the Researcher

10. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

10.1 Correlation between Saving and Borrowing

H_{n1}: There is no significant correlation between saving and borrowing

H_{a1}: There is significant correlation between saving and borrowing

Table No – 1: Saving and Borrowing

		Saving	Borrowing
Saving	Correlation	1	0.397**
	Sig.		.000
	Respondents(N)	209	209
Borrowing	Correlation	0.397**	1
	Sig.	.000	
	Respondents(N)	209	209

@1%

Table 1 show that the correlation coefficient between saving and borrowing is 0.397. It's an indication of a strong association between two items. The computed coefficient of correlation has statistical significance at the 1% level of significance. As a result, the null hypothesis can be ruled out and the alternate hypothesis accepted. It's acceptable to think that saving and borrowing are two notions that are connected.

10.2 Correlation between Saving and Self-Dependent

H_{n2}: There is no significant correlation between saving and self-dependent

H_{a2}: There is significant correlation between saving and self-dependent

Table No – 2: Saving and Self-Dependent

		Saving	Self-Dependent
Saving	Correlation	1	0.655**
	Sig.		.000
	Respondents(N)	209	209
Self-Dependent	Correlation	0.655**	1
	Sig.	.000	
	Respondents(N)	209	209

@1%

According to Table -2, the correlation coefficient between saving and self-reliance appears to be 0.655. It denotes the existence of a positive relationship between two variables. At the 1% level of significance, the estimated correlation coefficient is statistically significant. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected, whereas the alternative hypothesis is accepted. It seems reasonable to assume that saving and self-reliance are linked.

10.3 Correlation between Self-Dependent and Planning

H_{n3}: There is no significant correlation between self-dependent and Planning

H_{a3}: There is significant correlation between self-dependent and Planning

Table No – 3: Self-Dependent and Planning

		Self-Dependent	Planning
Self-Dependent	Correlation	1	0.652 ^{**}
	Sig.		.000
	Respondents(N)	209	209
Planning	Correlation	0.652 ^{**}	1
	Sig.	.000	
	Respondents(N)	209	209

@1%

The value of the coefficient of association between self-dependent and planning is 0.652, according to table 3. It denotes the existence of a positive relationship between two variables. At a 1% level of significance, the obtained coefficient of correlation is judged to be significant. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected, whereas the alternative hypothesis is accepted. It appears reasonable to conclude that self-reliance and planning are intertwined.

10.4 Correlation between Borrowing and Planning

H_{n4}: There is no significant correlation between borrowing and planning

H_{n5}: There is significant correlation between borrowing and planning

Table No – 4: Borrowing and Planning

		Borrowing	Planning
Borrowing	Correlation	1	0.378 ^{**}
	Sig.		.000
	Respondents(N)	209	209
Planning	Correlation	0.378 ^{**}	1
	Sig.	.000	
	Respondents(N)	209	209

@1%

According to table 4, the coefficient of connection between borrowing and planning is 0.378. It indicates that two variables have a positive association. At the 1% level of significance, the obtained coefficient of correlation is significant. The null hypothesis is thereby rejected, while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. It's logical to assume that borrowing and planning are linked. This indicates that there is a significant link between these two sets of data.

10.5 One-way ANOVA - Age Groups Vs Various Dimensions

H_{n5}: Age groups have no significant difference between the variables saving, borrowing, investment, planning and self-dependent.

H_{a5}: Age groups have significant difference between the variables saving, borrowing, investment, planning and self-dependent.

Table No: 5

Dimensions		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Saving	Between Groups	516.347	4	129.087	1.635	.167
	Within Groups	16109.997	204	78.971		
	Total	16626.344	208			
Borrowing	Between Groups	267.024	4	66.756	3.848	.005
	Within Groups	3538.852	204	17.347		
	Total	3805.876	208			
Investment	Between Groups	38.597	4	9.649	4.031	.004
	Within Groups	488.284	204	2.394		
	Total	526.880	208			
Planning	Between Groups	225.549	4	56.387	3.345	.011
	Within Groups	3438.671	204	16.856		
	Total	3664.220	208			
Self-Dependent	Between Groups	60.605	4	15.151	.712	.585
	Within Groups	4341.443	204	21.282		
	Total	4402.048	208			

* @5%

The null hypothesis is rejected since the p values are at the significant threshold of 0.05, implying that there is a statistically significant difference between the age groups and the variables of borrowing, investment, and planning. The null hypothesis is accepted because the p-values for the other research variables are not significant. Hence, borrowing, investing, and planning differ greatly by age group. There are no substantial differences between age groups when it comes to the factors saving and self-reliance.

10.6 One-way ANOVA - Education Groups Vs Various Dimensions

H_{n6}: Education groups have no significant difference between the variables saving, borrowing, investment, planning and self-dependent.

H_{a6}: Education groups have significant difference between the variables saving, borrowing, investment, planning and self-dependent.

Table No: 6

Dimensions		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Saving	Between Groups	557.615	3	185.872	2.371	.072
	Within Groups	16068.729	205	78.384		
	Total	16626.344	208			
Borrowing	Between Groups	150.669	3	50.223	2.817	.040
	Within Groups	3655.206	205	17.830		
	Total	3805.876	208			
Investment	Between Groups	12.657	3	4.219	1.682	.172
	Within Groups	514.224	205	2.508		
	Total	526.880	208			
Planning	Between Groups	189.893	3	63.298	3.735	.012
	Within Groups	3474.327	205	16.948		
	Total	3664.220	208			
Self-Dependent	Between Groups	35.871	3	11.957	.561	.641
	Within Groups	4366.177	205	21.298		
	Total	4402.048	208			

* @5%

Because the p values are at the significant threshold of 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected, showing that there is a statistically significant difference between the education groups and factors such as borrowing and planning. Because the p-values for the other research variables are not significant, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, borrowing and planning change greatly depending on the educational degree. When it comes to saving, investing, and being self-sufficient, there are no significant differences in education levels.

11. FINDINGS

- The coefficient of association between the variables saving and borrowing, saving and self-dependent, self-dependent and Planning, borrowing and planning is positive in the correlation test. At the 1% level of significance, the obtained coefficient of correlation is significant. The null hypothesis is thereby rejected, while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Saving and borrowing, saving and self-reliance, self-reliance and Planning, borrowing and planning are all connected in some way. This indicates that there is a significant link between these two sets of data.
- Borrowing and planning differ significantly across educational levels, according to a one-way ANOVA test across education factor. When it comes to saving, investing, and being self-sufficient, there are no significant differences in education levels.
- The age groups differ significantly in terms of borrowing, investing, and planning, according to a one-way ANOVA test across the age factor. There are no substantial differences between age groups when it comes to the factors saving and self-reliance.

12. SUGGESTIONS

The government and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) should take the required efforts to raise financial literacy and educate people about the best ways to invest their money. The respondents were also found to be not keeping proper records of their financial affairs. It is advised that comprehensive training and workshops be done among the rural and

semi-urban areas on how to keep their household accounts for better financial management. In terms of financial products, insurance was shown to be a popular choice among non-working women in Karnataka. There are some additional most beneficial financial items that should be made aware among the respondents, such as mutual funds, KVP, post office saving scheme, and so on, so that the respondents can profit.

CONCLUSION

Because of the information technology era, everyone has access to a wealth of information in various fields of education, empowering individuals to improve their quality of life. Women's education and empowerment have become increasingly important in developing countries like India in recent years. Financial literacy is an important factor that contributes to a country's economic prosperity especially among women, irrespective of them being employed. The economy's growth rate will be boosted by a better comprehension of financial information and a favourable attitude toward financial planning and investment. This study indicated that financial literacy has an impact on financial planning of non-working women in order to avoid unfavourable outcomes as a result of today's more challenging situations not only in the households but also economy as a whole. People must therefore understand financial literacy in order to make sound financial decisions.

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